

Psychological Determinants of Political Inclusion: Examining the Roles of Interpersonal Insensitivity, Psychological Inflexibility, and Self-Concept Among Rural Voters

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Abstract

This study investigates the influence of interpersonal insensitivity, psychological inflexibility, and self-concept on perceived political inclusion among rural voters. The objectives include examining the extent to which each factor—interpersonal insensitivity, psychological inflexibility, and self-concept—impacts perceptions of political inclusion within this demography. A cross-sectional survey design was employed, collecting data from 386 registered voters across nine local government areas in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The findings reveal that while interpersonal insensitivity and psychological inflexibility exhibit indirect relationships with perceived political inclusion, self-concept emerges as a significant and direct predictor. These results highlight the complex interplay between individual psychological traits and perceptions of political inclusion, which helps emphasise the pivotal role of self-concept in fostering a sense of belonging within political contexts. It was therefore recommended, among others, that community programmes that promote self-esteem and inclusive communication to engage under-represented demographics be implemented.

Keywords: *political inclusion, interpersonal sensitivity, psychological inflexibility, self-concept, rural voters*

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1. Introduction

The framework of human relationships inherently relies on inclusion and belongingness, which are the essential components of societal functioning (Abrams & Hogg, 2004). These dynamics of inclusion and exclusion significantly shape cultural and political alliances, reflecting a critical aspect of social life—determining who is included or excluded and the consequences thereof (Abrams et al., 2005). Inclusion not only enhances material interests (Caporael & Baron, 1997) and self-esteem (Leary & Baumeister, 2000; Tajfel & Turner, 1986) but also validates beliefs (Hogg & Abrams, 1993) and fosters distinctiveness and acceptance (Brewer, 1991).

On the other hand, politics plays a crucial role in shaping processes of inclusion, exclusion, and inequality, significantly influencing social and developmental changes (Acemoglu & Robinson, 2012; Fukuyama, 2011; Khan, 2010; North et al., 2009). In democratic societies, political inclusion is fundamental for ensuring equity and justice, granting individuals access to participate in decision-making processes. However, perceptions of political inclusion often vary, especially in contexts where systemic barriers and marginalisation persist.

Perceived political inclusion reflects the extent to which individuals believe that governmental policies, developmental activities, and resources address collective needs equitably. It encompasses fundamental rights such as voting, running for office, and influencing policy decisions. While democracy emphasizes inclusivity, individuals in minority groups may perceive inclusion only if systemic protections ensure equitable representation and influence.

Efforts to enhance political inclusion globally have seen strategies such as quotas for marginalised groups, gender parity laws, youth involvement, and indigenous community recognition. For example, India's reserved seats for Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes (Alam, 2015; Ambagudia, 2019) and Norway's gender quota law (Dahlerup, 2005) exemplify these measures. Scotland's reduction of the voting age to 16 (Mycock et al., 2020) and Ecuador's recognition of indigenous rights (Murphy, 2018) demonstrate innovative approaches to fostering inclusivity.

Interpersonal insensitivity, characterised by a lack of empathy and awareness, undermines perceptions of political inclusion by fostering alienation and

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marginalisation (Williams, 2007). Similarly, psychological inflexibility, marked by cognitive rigidity and emotional avoidance, may hinder meaningful political engagement (Hayes et al., 2012). Self-concept, encompassing identity and self-worth, further influences perceptions of inclusion, with individuals deriving agency from their social group memberships (Tajfel & Turner, 1979).

1.2 Significance of the Study

This research investigates the influence of interpersonal insensitivity, psychological inflexibility, and self-concept on perceived political inclusion among rural voters in Akwa Ibom State. By exploring an understudied dimension of social inclusion in Nigeria, the study significantly contributes to the body of knowledge in political psychology and sociopolitical dynamics.

The findings offer practical insights into the challenges of political inclusion within the Nigerian context, providing a foundation for addressing systemic and psychological barriers to equitable participation. These insights hold potential for reshaping political norms while helping to foster a more inclusive and people-centred governance structure and promoting leadership that reflects the diverse needs of society.

Furthermore, the study also sparks a national discourse on political inclusiveness, encouraging policies and interventions that strengthen democratic principles and foster an egalitarian society. The implications of this research extend beyond the immediate context, opening avenues for future investigations into the roles of psychological constructs—interpersonal insensitivity, psychological inflexibility, and self-concept—in shaping perceptions of political inclusion.

1.3 Statement of the Problem

Political inclusion, a cornerstone of democratic governance, remains a persistent challenge for many nations, despite its importance. Citizens often struggle to connect their needs with accountable and representative political institutions; this fosters mistrust and feelings of marginalisation. Global inequalities, such as gender disparities and the under-representation of minority groups, exacerbate this issue. For instance, women, who constitute nearly half the world's population, are significantly under-represented in political leadership roles, and systemic barriers limit marginalised groups' access to political representation. These disparities perpetuate social

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inequalities and hinder the establishment of inclusive democratic systems (World Bank, 2022; Chandra, 2007).

In Nigeria, the issue is particularly acute. Gender inequality in political representation is evident, with only 20 women elected to the 10th National Assembly out of 469 seats (PLAC, 2023). Socioeconomic factors, such as poverty and limited resources, further exclude marginalised communities from active political participation. Additionally, the low engagement of youth in political processes highlights a missed opportunity for intergenerational dialogue and inclusion. These systemic barriers undermine the principles of equity and representation, thereby emphasising the urgent need for frameworks that promote inclusive political participation and address the diverse needs of Nigeria's population.

1.4 Research Questions

The study seeks to answer the following questions:

- i. Will interpersonal insensitivity influence the perception of political inclusion among rural voters?
- ii. Will psychological inflexibility influence the perception of political inclusion among rural voters?
- iii. Will self-concept influence the perception of political inclusion among rural voters?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

In the course of the study, the following hypotheses were tested:

- i. Interpersonal insensitivity will significantly influence the perception of political inclusion among rural voters.
- ii. Psychological inflexibility will significantly influence the perception of political inclusion among rural voters.
- iii. Self-concept will significantly influence the perception of political inclusion among rural voters.

1.6 Research Objectives

1. To examine the influence of interpersonal insensitivity on the perception of political inclusion among rural voters.

2. To investigate how psychological inflexibility impacts the perception of political inclusion among rural voters.
3. To assess the role of self-concept in shaping the perception of political inclusion among rural voters.

Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this study draws on three key theories that explore the relationship between group belongingness and individuality: Optimal Distinctiveness Theory (ODT), Self-Determination Theory (SDT), and Social Identity Theory (SIT). These theories provide valuable insights into how individuals navigate their sense of identity and inclusion in political contexts.

2.1.1 Optimal Distinctiveness Theory (ODT) posits that individuals strive for a balance between the need for inclusion within social groups and the desire for distinctiveness (Brewer, 1991; Brewer & Roccas, 2001). In political systems, this balance manifests as individuals aligning with groups that reflect their unique values while ensuring a sense of belonging. This dynamic underscores the importance of designing inclusive systems that acknowledge the distinctiveness of diverse groups, thus enhancing engagement and representation.

2.1.2 Self-Determination Theory (SDT) emphasises the fulfilment of psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness as crucial for motivation and well-being (Deci & Ryan, 1991, 2000). In the political sphere, SDT highlights the importance of providing citizens with autonomy-supportive practices, opportunities for competence development through political literacy, and fostering a sense of relatedness through inclusive policies. These elements are foundational for meaningful political participation and inclusion.

2.1.3 Social Identity Theory (SIT) explains how individuals derive a sense of self from their group memberships (Tajfel & Turner, 1979). SIT highlights the significance of in-group favouritism and social comparison in shaping perceptions of political inclusion. Political systems that promote the visibility and influence of diverse groups strengthen voters' sense of inclusion, while the marginalisation of certain groups leads to disillusionment and disengagement.

Together, these theories illuminate the interplay between individuality and group belongingness, offering a comprehensive lens for examining the factors that influence political inclusion among rural voters.

2.2 Empirical Review

2.2.1 Interpersonal Insensitivity and Perceived Political Inclusion

Studies highlight the negative impact of interpersonal insensitivity on political inclusion. Schildkraut (2005) found that exposure to exclusionary political rhetoric significantly reduced political efficacy among immigrant groups, emphasising the need for inclusive messaging to enhance engagement. Similarly, Baumeister et al. (2007) noted that social exclusion leads to emotional insensitivity and impaired self-regulation, which can hinder political participation. Hopkins (2011) revealed that perceived discrimination by political representatives reduces trust and engagement among minority groups. Additionally, Tuscherer et al. (2016) demonstrated that unfair exclusion weakens efficacy needs and increases antisocial tendencies, underscoring the importance of fairness in political processes.

2.2.2 Psychological Inflexibility and Perceived Political Inclusion

Psychological inflexibility, characterised by rigidity in beliefs and avoidance of diverse perspectives, is linked to political exclusion. Rock and Janoff-Bulman (2010) associated cognitive rigidity with conservatism, showing its influence on political orientation and reduced adaptability. Levin et al. (2016) found that psychological inflexibility significantly predicted generalised prejudice, limiting political inclusivity. Zmigrod et al. (2020) further connected cognitive inflexibility to extreme partisanship across political ideologies. These findings highlight the adverse effects of rigidity on engagement in inclusive political systems.

2.2.3 Self-Concept and Perceived Political Inclusion

Self-concept significantly influences political inclusion. Schildkraut (2005) reported that individuals who feel their social identities are valued exhibit higher civic engagement and trust in political institutions. Negative self-concepts, as Banaszak et al.

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(2010) observed, are associated with reduced political participation and perceptions of inclusion. Interventions promoting positive self-concepts, as shown by Haslam et al. (2008), enhance inclusivity by affirming identities and challenging stereotypes. These studies emphasise the critical role of self-concept in fostering inclusive and participatory political environments.

Research Design and Methodology

This study employed a cross-sectional survey design to collect data from participants. A structured questionnaire was used to gather insights on interpersonal insensitivity, psychological inflexibility, self-concept, and their impact on perceived political inclusion among rural voters. This design was chosen for its ability to capture a snapshot of the population's experiences and perspectives within a specific period. It enables comprehensive analysis of the variables under investigation.

3.1 Area

The research was conducted in nine local government areas (LGAs) across Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, selected from its three senatorial districts: Eket (Eket, Mkpatt Enin, and Onna), Ikot Ekpene (Abak, Ikot Ekpene, and Oruk Anam), and Uyo (Etinan, Nsit Ibom, and Nsit Ubium). Akwa Ibom, created in 1987, spans 7,249 square kilometres with a population of approximately 7.2 million people and an annual growth rate of 3.4%. It is bounded by Rivers, Cross Rivers, and Abia States, as well as the Gulf of Guinea. The state's economy is diversified, with activities such as farming, fishing, trading, and public sector employment playing central roles. These selected LGAs reflect a mix of urban, semi-urban, and rural communities, making them ideal for examining political inclusion dynamics among diverse populations.

3.2 Population and Sampling Technique

The study population comprised approximately 780,155 registered voters across the nine LGAs. A sample size of 386 participants was determined using Yamane's formula with a 5% error margin. A multistage cluster sampling technique was employed to ensure representativeness. First, three LGAs were selected from each senatorial district, based on voter registration data showing the least voter engagement in pre-2023 compared to pre-2019 elections. Purposive sampling was then used to select participants

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aged 18 and above who were registered voters residing within the selected LGAs. These criteria ensured that the sample accurately reflected the target demographic for the study.

4.1 Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 4.1: Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)
Sex		
Male	222	57.5
Female	164	42.5
Total	386	100.0
Age		
18-24	139	36.0
25-34	152	39.4
35-44	75	19.4
45-54	15	3.9
55-64	4	1.0
65+	1	.3
Total	386	100.0
Local Govt		
Abak	45	11.7
Eket	32	8.3
Etinan	55	14.2
Ikot Ekpene	61	15.8
Mkpat Enin	51	13.2
Nsit Ibom	49	12.7
Nsit Ubium	32	8.3
Onna	27	7.0
Oruk Anam	34	8.8
Total	386	100.0

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Education Level

SSCE	104	26.9
ND	58	15.0
HND/BSC	205	53.1
MSc	17	4.4
PhD	2	.5
Total	386	100.0

Marital Status

Single	254	65.8
Married	127	32.9
Seperated	1	.3
Widowed	4	1.0
Total	386	100.0

Table 4.1 provides an overview of the demographic characteristics of the study participants, a total of 386 individuals. The sample comprised 57.5% males and 42.5% females. Educational qualifications varied, with over half of the participants holding a first-degree certificate (BSc/HND) at 32.3%, while others possessed SSCE, ND, MSc, or PhD qualifications. The participants were drawn from nine local government areas in Akwa Ibom State, with the highest representation from Ikot Ekpene (15.8%). In terms of age distribution, the majority (75.4%) were between 18 and 34 years old. Regarding marital status, 65.8% of the participants were single, while 32.9% were married.

Table 4.2 Showing Zero-Order Correlation Among the Independent Variables, Sex, and the Dependent Variable

S/N	Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	Political Inclusion							
2	Interpersonal Insensitivity	.122*						
3	Psychological Inflexibility	.120*	.094					
4	Self-Concept	-.258**	-.240**	.100*				
5	Sex	-.090	-.121*	.007	.134**			
6	2023 Elections	-.220**	-.176**	.005	.182**	.135**		
7	Future Elections	-.086	-.111*	-.091	.126*	.067	.134**	

*. $p = 0.05$

**. $p = 0.01$

Table 4.2 presents zero-order correlation among the independent variables, sex, and the dependent variable in the study. The result shows that perceived political inclusion correlated significantly with interpersonal insensitivity ($r = 0.122, p < .05$), psychological inflexibility ($r = 0.120, p < .05$) and self-concept ($r = -0.258, p < .01$). On the other hand, there was no significant correlation between perceived political inclusion and sex ($r = -0.090, p > .05$) and intention to vote in future elections ($r = -0.086, p > .05$), while participation in the last election correlated significantly with perceived political inclusion ($r = -0.220, p < .01$).

Table 4.3: Multiple Regression Model showing the Effect of Interpersonal Insensitivity, Psychological Inflexibility and Self-Concept on Political Inclusion.

Variable	Mean	SD	R	R ²	F	df	p	β	t	p
			0.300	0.090	12.591	3	.001			
Interpersonal Insensitivity	17.56	5.54						0.046	0.910	> .05
Psychological Inflexibility	30.13	6.94						0.142	2.875	< .05
Self-Concept	119.49	21.79						0.261	5.148	.001

$N = 386$; Dependent Variable: Political Inclusion

Table 4.3 presents the multiple regression model showing the prediction of political inclusion by interpersonal insensitivity, psychological inflexibility and self-concept. The result shows that independent variables jointly and significantly predicted political inclusion among the study participants ($R^2 = 0.090$, $F(3, 382) = 12.591$, $p < .001$) accounting for 9% ($R^2 = 0.090$) variance in political inclusion.

The result further indicated that interpersonal insensitivity did not independently contribute to the prediction of political inclusion ($b = 0.046$; $t = 0.910$; $p > .05$). On the other hand, psychological inflexibility ($b = 0.142$; $t = 2.875$; $p < .05$) and self-concept ($b = -0.261$; $t = -5.148$; $p < .05$) significantly and independently predicted political inclusion.

4.2 Discussion of Findings

This study explored the influence of interpersonal insensitivity, psychological inflexibility, and self-concept on perceived political inclusion among rural voters. The findings revealed significant correlations between these variables and political inclusion, offering valuable insights into the psychological and social dynamics of political engagement. The analysis was guided by Optimal Distinctiveness Theory (ODT), Self-Determination Theory (SDT), and Social Identity Theory (SIT), providing a robust framework for understanding these relationships.

4.2.1 Interpersonal Insensitivity and Political Inclusion

Interpersonal insensitivity showed a positive correlation with perceived political inclusion ($r = 0.122$, $p < .05$). This unexpected finding suggests that individuals with higher levels of interpersonal insensitivity may perceive themselves as more politically included, possibly because they are less attuned to social exclusion or critical cues. From an ODT perspective, such individuals may achieve a balance between distinctiveness and inclusion by focusing on their alignment with group norms, rather than interpersonal nuances. These findings underscore the complexity of how insensitivity interacts with political engagement, warranting further investigation into its broader implications.

4.2.2 Psychological Inflexibility and Political Inclusion

A significant positive correlation was also observed between psychological inflexibility and perceived political inclusion ($r = 0.120, p < .05$). Psychological rigidity may help individuals align with specific political ideologies or group norms, fostering a sense of belonging. While this appears counterintuitive given the adaptability benefits of flexibility, ODT suggests that rigid adherence to norms in well-defined community settings can reinforce inclusion. However, SDT implies that such engagement may lack autonomy, driven instead by controlled motivations. This highlights a need for deeper exploration of the nuanced role of psychological flexibility in fostering inclusive political systems.

4.2.3 Self-Concept and Political Inclusion

Self-concept demonstrated a significant negative correlation with political inclusion ($r = -0.258, p < .01$), indicating that individuals with lower self-concept perceive greater exclusion. This aligns with ODT and SDT, which emphasise the importance of balancing self-worth and group alignment. Low self-notion may undermine perceptions of competence and belonging, limiting political engagement. The strong predictive power of self-concept ($b = -0.261, t = -5.148, p < .05$) underscores its critical role in shaping political inclusion, suggesting targeted interventions to enhance self-esteem could promote broader engagement.

These findings collectively illuminate the interplay of psychological traits in shaping perceptions of political inclusion, emphasising the need for inclusive practices that address these dynamics in rural contexts.

5.1 Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

This study investigated the relationship between political inclusion and psychological variables such as interpersonal insensitivity, psychological inflexibility, and self-concept among rural voters. The findings revealed significant positive correlations between political inclusion and both interpersonal insensitivity ($r = 0.122, p < .05$) and psychological inflexibility ($r = 0.120, p < .05$). Conversely, a significant negative

correlation was observed between political inclusion and self-concept ($r = -0.258$, $p < .01$), indicating that lower self-esteem is associated with higher perceived inclusion.

Interestingly, no significant correlations were found between political inclusion and sex ($r = -0.090$, $p > .05$) or intention to vote in future elections ($r = -0.086$, $p > .05$). However, participation in the last election showed a negative correlation with political inclusion ($r = -0.220$, $p < .01$), suggesting that recent electoral engagement might diminish perceptions of inclusion. Regression analysis highlighted psychological inflexibility ($b = 0.142$; $t = 2.875$; $p < .05$) and self-concept ($b = -0.261$; $t = -5.148$; $p < .05$) as significant predictors of political inclusion, collectively accounting for 9% of the variance ($R^2 = 0.090$, $F(3, 382) = 12.591$, $p < .001$). These results underscore the complex interplay of psychological factors shaping perceptions of political inclusion.

5.2 Conclusion

The study provides valuable insights on the psychological dimensions of political inclusion. While interpersonal insensitivity and psychological inflexibility may influence perceptions indirectly, self-concept emerged as a critical and direct determinant of political inclusion. These findings align with Optimal Distinctiveness Theory, Self-Determination Theory, and Social Identity Theory, which emphasise the interplay of psychological traits and group dynamics in political engagement. The lack of significant correlations with sex and future voting intentions, alongside the significant relationship with past electoral participation, highlights the multifaceted nature of political inclusion. This research contributes to a deeper understanding of how social identities and individual psychological characteristics shape political inclusion, offering a foundation for future studies and interventions.

5.3 Recommendations

From the conclusion drawn, the following recommendations are made:

- I. Community programmes that promote self-esteem, civic participation, and volunteerism should be prioritised to strengthen individuals' self-concept and foster a greater sense of political inclusion.

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Luckyimoh D. Inyang; Dr. Iboro F. A. Ottu; Lucky O. Abogoh

- ii. Further research should explore the negative correlation between recent electoral participation and perceived inclusion, which will help identify potential sources of disenchantment or exclusion.
- iii. Targeted efforts should be made to engage under-represented demographics through inclusive communication and participation strategies that can help create a more politically inclusive environment.
- iv. Educational initiatives aimed at enhancing political literacy and awareness can empower individuals, by increasing their confidence and fostering meaningful political inclusion. Such programmes should emphasise the value of diverse perspectives and active participation in democratic processes.

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